

PROCESSING OF DASAWISMA GROUP WASTE RECYCLING IN GADING KASRI URBAN VILLAGE MALANG CITY

Candra Wahyu Hidayat,¹ Andi Nu Graha²

^{1,2} Kanjuruhan University Malang, Indonesia
Corresponding Author: candra@unikama.ac.id

Abstract: *This service is used to provide benefits to the community regarding how to manage waste from community members in the Dasawisma group Urban Village, Malang. All this management is used for community empowerment in the Urban Village environment. With the gathering of all citizens, it is hoped that the income of the dasawisma group will increase and become a benefit for the residents. The use of waste and training on waste management are expected to be the starting point of the success of the dasawisma group, which is supported by residents of the whole Urban Village, Malang. Eventually, the development business unit of the dasawisma group emerged, such as sustainable management which could empower the environment of residents and increase family income.*

Keywords: *innovation, training, socialization*

I. INTRODUCTION

The Dasawisma group consists of housewives who live in the village of Gading Kasri. The product of this waste recycling is the result of sorting rubbish that was disposed of by the residents of Gading Kasri Urban Village. The waste sorting is based on 3 R (Reuse, Reduce, Recycle) the rest which cannot be processed is disposed of in a landfill. This sorting of waste starts with the collection of rubbish from each citizen.

To meet the needs of waste is felt not optimal because almost all residents do not understand and do not understand about the management and benefits of waste management. Then regarding waste management is still very simple. The addition of facilities and infrastructure as well as the management of waste segregation is necessary to increase the volume of production, but again it is still experiencing difficulties in accessing information to residents and collecting waste.

There are several expectations from members that would be realized during discussions during the survey to the location, namely:

1. There is no comprehensive socialization to all RWs in Gading Kasri Urban Village about waste management system.

2. Facilitation in management is still traditional.
3. Facilitation of production facilities and infrastructure in the form of waste sorting equipment, trash bins, for processing waste and increasing production capacity.
4. Assistance in terms of financial management and marketing.

Based on the determination of priority problems faced by partners (the Dasawisma Group) which have been mutually agreed upon are as follows:

1. Lack of public awareness about the importance of good waste management.
2. Lack of information dissemination in waste management to residents, especially RWs in Gading Kasri Urban Village
3. The financial management process which is still traditional.
4. The operational management process that runs manually.
5. Knowledge and information about a good waste management system.

Based on the priority problems that have been described above, the agreed solution will be implemented through the application of several science and technology to help solve the problem are as follows:

1. Socialization and training with the Dasawisma Group to all RW residents. Because socialization is an important aspect in increasing the knowledge, attitudes and perceptions of the community regarding the importance of waste management, continuous information is needed on this waste management in cooperation with all parties, especially the Urban Village, RW Heads and RT Heads in Gading Kasri Urban Village. By involving all parties, it is expected that the socialization will run optimally so that waste can provide a great benefit to the Dasawisma Group itself.
2. This waste management must meet good operational standards, especially in administrative standards in the fields of management, finance and marketing. Standardization of waste management is necessary to produce operational management, financial management, and better marketing. By providing training and mentoring, as well as ongoing modules, it is expected to be able to increase the attitude of independence and professionalism of each member of the dasawisma.

This community service program emphasizes the application of science and technology is expected to provide outcomes:

1. Increasing socialization and training to citizens is expected to be able to increase income and benefit from increasing waste collection.
2. Increased knowledge and technology skills, known to be able to improve the performance of managers so that with the consistency of management can improve product quality and increase product volume as measured by comparing the results of pre-test and post-test.

3. Enhancing technological knowledge and skills, known by measuring the time of pre-test and post-test waste collection.
4. Compilation of financial, marketing and entrepreneurship training modules arranged according to group needs so that they are applicable. This module also outlines detailed steps in designing financial, marketing and entrepreneurship activities so that the group is expected to be able to innovate in developing its products independently.

II. METHOD

The method of implementing the Science and Technology Community Service Grant (I_bM) to be held uses the method of: SOCIALIZATION and TRAINING. In this activity, explained the importance of business management which includes Financial Management, Marketing Management, entrepreneurship in a business management Alma (2010). Marketing can also be interpreted as activities and the creation and submission of a welfare level to members of the Assauri community (2007). In addition to training, assistance is also provided in administrative governance both financially and marketing.

The community that became the target of the implementation of Science and Technology Service for the Community (I_bM) is the Dasawisma Group located in Gading Kasri Urban Village, Klojen District, Malang.

The importance of a comprehensive and comprehensive understanding of the importance of business management and innovation in business management activities. Business management cannot be separated from various business activities, other than that business management is an inseparable aspect of entrepreneurial activities.

It is expected that with a good understanding of the functions and roles of business management in various aspects of life, it can increase public awareness in entrepreneurship, to improve their standard of living.

The conceptual framework of service that is transferred to the community

Figure 1: Conceptual framework for the implementation of science and technology for the community (IbM)

III. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Business management is a plan related to how a person can process or manage a series of businesses from selecting members to solving problems. Business management will require a lot of quality human resources (HR) and this includes several things. According to Sule and Saefullah (2010) there are several basic management principles that need to be considered: First, the Human Resources Aspect is closely related to the allocation of resources related to the organization, so that the managerial side is a further consequence in achieving organizational effectiveness. Second, the directing and implementation aspects can only be implemented if the allocation of human resources has been carried out within the organization. The third aspect of determining the position in the right place is also an important factor in the organization. Fourth, because management is a social science that cannot be separated by any field of science. Fifth, Culture; the values that underlie the managerial behavior of an institution in achieving its objectives within the company are known as Corporate Culture. So management is an integration that allows for the emergence of togetherness in the environment of human resources in an organization, so it is very potential in achieving organizational goals. It is expected that from this service the community will get added value from the waste that has been sorted and turned into quality goods so that it can improve the welfare of the community.

Documentation of community service activities

REFERENCES

- Alma Buchari, *Pengantar Bisnis*, Alfabeta, Bandung, 2010.
- Assauri Sofjan, *Manajemen Pemasaran*, PT. Raja Grafindo Persada, Jakarta, 2007.
- Sule dan Saefullah, *Pengantar Manajemen*, Kencana Prenada Media Group, Jakarta, 2010.